

Molecular design through TD-DFT calculation of chiral salen Cu^{II} complexes toward NIR absorption for DSSC

Marin Yamaguchi, Keita Takahashi and Takashiro Akitsu*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Tokyo University of Science, 1-3 Kagurazaka, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo 162-8601, Japan

E-mail : akitsu@rs.kagu.tus.ac.jp

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Abstract : DSSC (Dye sensitized solar cell) has been researched by many laboratories and dye is main material for the cell. In this study, we designed new six complexes for dye. For effective NIR absorption of cell, these complexes have π -conjugated and electron withdrawing group. To see the effect of this group on the complexes, we gained the calculated UV-Vis spectra of complexes. As a result, NIR shift by π -conjugated and electron withdrawing was seen. Experimental UV-Vis spectra of complexes that have electron withdrawing group were also measured. We can expect the DSSC that has effective NIR absorption from this study.

Keywords : Molecular design, TD-DFT calculation, Cu^{II} complexes, NIR absorption, DSSC (Dye sensitized solar cell).

Introduction

DSSC was invented by Gratzel and it has different character from conventional silicon type solar cell in point of ease at fabrication¹. This would make DSSC low cost when we concern the time and level of factory. The color of DSSC can be changed by dye used on the cell². So DSSC also has advantage at design. Though it has many better points, DSSC has not been used at industrial region because of its low energy efficiency. Beside the efficiency of silicon type solar cells are more than 20%, efficiency of DSSC contains famous dye (N3,N719,N749) is around or less than 10%³⁻⁵. One of the reasons of inferior efficiency is limited absorption of cells. UV-Vis absorption spectra of many cells show that absorption area is limited among the UV-Vis band and absorption at NIR band cannot be seen. There is another problem of DSSC. Most of the cells that has high efficiency among DSSC contains ruthenium complex as dye. This makes DSSC high cost. Now researchers are studying to overcome these points.

Using dye that has π -conjugated system to expand absorption band toward NIR band was reported⁶⁻⁹. El-Shafei and others reported DSSC dye that has π -conjugated carbazole antenna as electron donor. In this report,

delocalization at HOMO arises from π -conjugated system makes strong intraligand transition to anchoring group⁶. Report by He *et al.* showed the effect of π -conjugated molecule on energy band. Decrease of LUMOs by π -extended area result in short HOMO-LUMO gap and NIR shift of absorption band in this report⁸. Ruthenium free donor- π -acceptor organic dye was also reported to make cell low cost¹⁰⁻¹². But organic dyes have complicated structure to synthesize and have low efficiency than ruthenium DSSCs. So metal complex without ruthenium would be expected for DSSC.

Along with discussion about efficiency, making solar cell frame retardant is now studied as new topic. Many patents about this are obtained in these three years. Talking about frame retardant materials, bromine substituted molecular for fire resistance was studied¹³. For example, bromine salen complex was studied about frame retardant PMMA¹⁴. From these points, using bromine complex for dye can be expected for flame retardant of DSSC.

Molecular design

In our laboratory, chiral salen Cu^{II} complexes have been studied. Molecular design of salen type ligand is easy and it can be synthesized easily by amine and aldehyde in alcohol at 313 K. Copper(II) complex that has

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of complex 1, 2-(1)-(4), 3.

effective NIR absorption can be good dye even ruthenium is not used. Moreover, red-shift due to dipole-dipole interactions in chiral complex was reported, which results in NIR shift^{15,16}. These points considered, our purpose is to design new four types of complexes that contain bromine as electron withdrawing group and extended π -conjugated system for DSSC dyes absorbing NIR light. Effect of electron-withdrawing group for NIR absorption DSSC has not reported many to the best of our knowledge, so we want to study the effect of electron withdrawing group. And bromine might be expected for flame retardant cell. After design, calculated absorption spectra by TD-DFT method and comparing these complexes. Complexes 1-3 (2-(1), (2), (3), (4) have $X_1, X_2, X_3 = H, H, H; Br, H, H; Br, Br, H; Br, Br, Br$, respectively) (Fig. 1, Table 1).

Table 1. Atoms on the complexes

	2-(1)	2-(2)	2-(3)	2-(4)
X_1	H	Br	Br	Br
X_2	H	H	Br	Br
X_3	H	H	H	Br

Methods

All calculations were performed using the Gaussian 09W software Revision A.02 (Gaussian, Inc.)¹⁷. Calculated UV-Vis spectrum was gained by TD-DFT with B3LYP functional. Basis sets were Lanl2DZ on copper to consider the effect core potential and 6-31G(d) on other atoms. Electron density and dipole moment were also gained by calculation. The effect of electron withdrawing group on NIR absorption was seen by comparison of calculated UV-Vis spectra of 2-(1)-(4). By comparing the calculated data of 1, 2-(1) and 3, we studied the effect of

π -conjugated system on NIR absorption. Moreover, we synthesized complexes 2-(1)-(4) and measured UV-Vis spectrum in DMSO.

Results and discussion

TD-DFT calculation :

Electron density :

Fig. 2 shows the electron density of all complexes. Red (black) means a lot of density and blue (gray) means relatively little density. All complexes have little density on the carboxyl group and dipole moments (Table 2) indicate toward carboxyl group. Comparing with 2-(1) to 2-(4), the color of naphthyl group at 2-(1) is yellow (light gray) and others show green (dark gray). This derives from electron withdrawing bromine of 2-(2),(3),(4).

Fig. 2. Electron density of each complex.

Table 2. Dipole moment

Complex number	Dipole moment (D)	Complex number	Dipole moment (D)
1	6.8509	2-(2)	7.3068
2-(1)	4.2201	2-(3)	4.5694
3	2.8357	2-(4)	6.4950

Excitation of each complex :

Fig. 3. Calculated UV-Vis spectra of **1**, **2** and **3**. Absorption intensity was adjusted to see the shift of peaks.

Complex **1** absorbs mainly at 315.1, 383.1 and 544.75 nm (Fig. 3). Absorption band at 315.1 and 383.1 nm are derived from intraligand transition and MLCT toward carboxyl group, so this would be effective absorption for DSSC. Peak at 544.75 nm is generated by LMCT. **2**-(1) absorbs at 329.03, 411.00 and 517.99 nm. The first two peaks are due to intraligand transition toward carboxyl group and the last one is LMCT (Figs. 4, 5). From these points, attribution of charge transfer to absorption band is similar at **1** and **2**-(1). The peaks of complex **3** are 373.24, 442.83 and 521.42 nm intraligand transition from π -conjugated group toward carboxyl group attributes the absorption band at 373.24 and 442.82 nm. Peak at 521.42 nm is generated by LMCT. Comparing the figure about molecular orbitals of after excitation, excitation toward carboxyl group of complex **3** is weaker than another two ones. This may be the effect of π -conjugated group to stabilize excited electron on benzene ring.

2-(2) absorbs at 330.15 nm and 513.86 nm. The first one is intraligand transition toward carboxyl group and the last one is LMCT. Absorption peaks of **2**-(3) are 325.72, 391.30 and 509.80 nm. The first peak is

Fig. 4. Electron figure of complex **1**, **2**-(1) and **3**. Before and after intraligand transition.

Fig. 5. Electron figure of complex 1, 2-(1) and 3. Before and after LMCT.

intraligand transition from benzene ring toward carboxyl group. The second peak is intraligand transition toward benzene ring on the left side. In this report left side means starting point of dipole moment. The peak at 509.80 nm is LMCT and intraligand transition toward center of complex. Strong absorption peak of 2-(3) from intraligand transition toward left side is appropriate among 2-(2),(3) and 2-(4). 2-(4) showed the peak at 344.39, 406.67, 421.15 and 512.64 nm. Peak at 344.39 nm is LMCT and little charge transfer toward carboxyl group from bromine atoms. The intraligand transition peak of 2-(4) toward carboxyl group might be overlapped by strong LMCT. Peaks at 406.67 and 421.15 nm are intraligand transition among benzene rings at left side and right side. Peak at 512.64 nm derives from LMCT which electron on bromine was attracted toward copper atom (Figs. 6–8).

Comparison of calculated UV-Vis spectra :

Peaks of intraligand transition toward carboxyl group showed the red-shift among complexes 1, 2-(1) and 3. But peaks of LMCT that are seen at 500–550 nm didn't show the red shift. Destabilization of HOMO area bands make the shorter energy gap between excitation concerned bands, and this made red shift of intraligand transition.

As for effect of electron withdrawing group, we compared the calculated spectra of 2-(1),(2),(3) and (4). Lowest wavelength peaks derive from intraligand transition to-

Fig. 6. Calculated UV-Vis spectra of 2-(1) to (4). Absorption intensity was adjusted to see the shift of peaks.

Fig. 7. Electron figure before and after peaks at the shortest wavelength of each complex. 2-(2),(3),(4).

ward carboxyl group at 2-(1), (2) and (3). But it was mainly LMCT at 2-(4). Regarding the intraligand transition peaks of 2-(1), (2) and (3), wavelengths of peaks were 2-(3) < 2-(1) < 2-(2). So the red-shift of intraligand transition by bromine was not seen. Absorption spectrum of 2-(3) has wide bands because of intraligand transition at 391.30 nm. This is characteristic excitation of this com-

Fig. 8. Electron figure of complex 2-(2),(3),(4). Before and after LMCT.

plex toward bromine at left side benzene ring. Bands of 2-(4) sited on longer wavelength than any other complexes. As a result, red shift of each complex by electron withdrawing group was not seen. But you can see the red shift of bands as a whole. This is because of stabilization of LUMO bands. The more bromine atoms exist on complex, the more stabilization of LUMO was there (Table 3).

Table 3. Attribution of excitation of each complex

Complex number	Wavelength (nm)	Excitation band	Complex number	Wavelength (nm)	Excitation band
1	315.10	HOMO→LUMO+2	2-(2)	330.15	HOMO-2→LUMO+2
	383.10	HOMO-2→LUMO		513.86	HOMO-4→LUMO
	544.75	HOMO-4→LUMO	2-(3)	325.72	HOMO-3→LUMO
2-(1)	329.03	HOMO-3→LUMO		391.30	HOMO→LUMO+1
	411.00	HOMO→LUMO+1		509.80	HOMO-4→LUMO
	517.99	HOMO-4→LUMO	2-(4)	344.39	HOMO-4→LUMO
3	373.24	HOMO→LUMO+3		406.67	HOMO→LUMO+1
	442.83	HOMO-1→LUMO+1		421.15	HOMO→LUMO
	521.42	HOMO-6→LUMO		512.64	HOMO-8→LUMO

Experimental UV-Vis spectra :

Fig. 9. UV-Vis spectra of 2-(1)-(4). Measured in DMSO 0.01 mM and absorption intensity were adjusted to see the shift of peaks.

From Figs. 5–9, peaks of 2-(2), (3) and (4) at 250–300 nm showed little red shift from 2-(1). The original peak of 2-(3) toward left side benzene ring that were seen at 391.30 nm on calculated spectrum was not seen at Fig. 5. Peaks of 2-(2) and (4) at 300–350 nm sited at longer wavelength than the others. Order of red-shift of peaks around 400 nm are 2-(1) < 2-(2) < 2-(3) < 2-(4). General consistence of absorption bands of calculated and experimental spectrum was not seen so we must improve the method of calculation.

Conclusion

Many studies showed the effect of π -conjugated group on red shift for better DSSC. In this study we also showed red shift of absorption band derive from bromine both by calculation and experiment. Red shift derived from π -conjugated system was also seen by calculation. Destabilization of HOMO of π -conjugated complex and stabilization of LUMO bands of bromine complex is the reason for red-shift. NIR absorption of dye has been one of the targets to improve efficiency of DSSC. And this will still be one of the main streams of study on DSSC. Discovery

of new dye that has effective and broad absorption toward NIR without ruthenium is expected.

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